

Integrating Safety Science into the design of future ships

Erin van Rheenen^{1,*}, Charlotte Löffler¹, Austin A. Kana¹, Johan T. Padding¹ and K. Visser¹

¹ Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands

Abstract. The maritime industry is under increasing pressure to innovate toward sustainability without compromising vessel safety. Emerging technologies, such as alternative fuels and advanced control systems, may reduce environmental impact but often introduce new risks, through increased complexity or reduction of the system's transparency. Current safety assessment methods typically overlook the human factor, which plays a critical role in accident occurrence and prevention. This paper applies safety science principles to analyse maritime safety approaches and develop safer vessel design guidelines. The analysis reveals that human failure typically results from design, organisational, or operational problems rather than being a standalone cause. To design inherently safer ships, human limitations must be considered from the outset. Overreliance on automation is problematic: while reducing workload, it does not guarantee increased safety, and complex system robustness is difficult to measure. Simplifying design enhances safety by reducing opportunities for failure. All technology should be designed with the human in mind: intuitive, accessible and resilient to human constraints. Design alone is insufficient; operational safety is equally critical. This requires resilient, human-centred systems with strong safety culture where problems are reported without victim blaming. Key findings of this paper include implementing standard safety steps (removing problems, barriers, and warnings), prioritising human-centred design, and fostering operational culture change. Expecting the unexpected, embracing uncertainty, and fostering human-machine cooperation are essential to achieving safer vessels and, by extension, a safer maritime sector. However, operational safety and a non-victim-blaming culture remain a significant area for improvement in the maritime industry.

Key words: Safety; Alternative Fuels; Safety Science; Control

1. Introduction

Since the sinking of the Titanic in 1912, maritime safety has increasingly become a central focal point within the industry. However, incidents and accidents with ships still occur regularly, with ships grounding or sinking resulting in deaths at least yearly. Research attributes the majority of accidents in the maritime sector to the human, even though the exact number accredited to this is debatable [1]. For example, one of the most recent large shipping accidents, the sinking of the HMNZS Manawanui, was attributed to human error [2]. Additionally, insurance companies such as Allianz share the view that 75% to even 96% of all accidents involve human error [3].

Next to enhancing safety, the maritime industry also wants to limit its greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions: the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set a goal for the industry to become net-zero GHG by 2050, as well as limits for NO_x emissions (as stipulated in Marpol Annex VI) [4, 5]. It is costly to reach these goals, and Allianz believes the investment in the crew will be reduced [3]. This reduction in investment will likely increase risks associated with human error.

One way to achieve the net-zero GHG goal is to use alternative fuels. However, this may have direct safety implications. While numerous alternative fuels are being explored, none can be considered inherently safe [6]. Nevertheless, it is important to note that conventional fuels such as marine diesel oil and heavy fuel oil also carry safety risks [6].

Let us now introduce hydrogen carriers as a class of alternative fuels based on hydrogen. Not all alternative fuels in the maritime industry are net-zero. Green hydrogen is net-zero, but storing hydrogen in its pure form poses energy density and safety issues. Therefore, other substances, including methanol

*Correspondence to: E.S.VanRheenen@tudelft.nl

and ammonia, are also explored to store hydrogen. When used like this, we call them hydrogen carriers. Hydrogen carriers are chemicals that can store and release hydrogen on demand. They often have a higher volumetric energy density and are generally considered safer than pure hydrogen [7]. Hydrogen carriers can be circular (the spent fuel can be hydrogenated again) or non-circular (such as ammonia and methanol). In the case of circular hydrogen carriers, the empty (dehydrogenated) fuel is brought back to shore to be rehydrogenated.

However, despite having a higher volumetric energy density than pure hydrogen, hydrogen carriers often have a lower energy density than conventionally used fuels such as marine diesel oil and heavy fuel oil. Thus, when aiming for a complete exchange of a vessel's operating fuel and energy system, efficiency increases become more and more relevant to maintain a similar autonomous travel distance, meaning the distance a vessel can travel without refuelling. While commonly used rule-based control systems perform reliably and well in their design conditions, they are limited in optimisation potential when diverging from those conditions [8]. Additionally, when NO_x emissions are fully capped, fuel cells may be required, which in turn often require some sort of reactor (e.g. a reformer) to operate. In combination with the trend towards electric power trains [9], the overall complexity of the ship energy system will increase [8]. Operating those more complex energy systems is an additional challenge for rule-based control [10]. Hence, the trend is going more and more towards advanced control, automation and optimization for vessel operation. These developments lead to more complex, more interconnected systems which require well-designed advanced operation control. This also enhances the system's fallibility if not properly accounted for in the design process. As a result, the safety of the vessel may be decreased.

To counteract this, safety both from system set-up and operation management perspective needs to become more significant already in the early-stage design process of modern vessels. We will look at this future vessel design from an integral perspective, considering how an alternatively fuelled vessel can be designed with high safety for humans, systems and operations. First, we will shortly introduce how the safety of systems and alternative fuels is currently assessed and why a rethinking of safety assessment might be needed (Section 2). Next, we will discuss both the safe integration of alternative fuels (Section 3) and the safety of the control system and operation (Section 4) in detail. To showcase our integral perspective, the insights from both topics will be combined in Section 5, to provide guidelines for safe vessel design, incorporating major safety science findings. We argue that by combining the safety assessment of the vessel in a holistic analysis, future vessel safety can be increased in the design process and allow for a safe integration of alternative fuels in global shipping.

2. Current Safety Assessment

As a United Nations body, the IMO sets standards for the construction and operation of international shipping. Originally, these conventions were rule-based, dictating exactly how a ship should be designed and built. Nowadays, the IMO is moving towards goal-based standards, which dictate that the ship has to be safe for the seafarers and the environment, whilst also being easily accessible for inspectors and maintenance crew. The movement towards goal-based standards is slow, changing one code at a time. The guidelines aim to ensure the ship's safety without limiting innovative design [11]. On the other hand, the standards are designed to be specific without leaving room for too much interpretation and are, consequently, developed for different codes, also outside of the ship construction domain [11].

There are several issues with the goal-based design approach, mainly because classifying things as safe is impossible. Many methods exist to estimate the safety of a system or process, but these all have major limitations. The following subsections briefly discuss the connection between the sustainability goals and the design process and safety of the vessel, the current methods used to assess safety and pinpoint the general, overarching issues associated with these methods.

2.1. How sustainability goals influence the vessel design process

Part of the UN sustainability goals' implementation results in the ambition of the IMO for the shipping industry to become net-zero emission by 2050. This ambition results in a drift towards many new, emission-reducing technologies such as electrification [9] to allow the integration of novel technologies, for

example, batteries. However, to meet the defined emission-reduction goals, the most important change for the maritime sector is the introduction of alternative fuels into vessel power trains [12].

These introduce a variety of different fuel aggregation states (gas, liquid or solid), safety characteristics, new components and other aspects into the design of new vessels, which aim to follow along the rules of the IMO.

While the amount of upcoming changes to maritime power trains are significant, some are more critical for the safety assessment than others. Previous research showed that the hazardous impact of alternative fuels can be quite severe [6]. As most future vessels will need to rely on alternative fuels in some form due to their required autonomous travel distance, getting insights into the safety of those novel and potentially hazardous substances is of high importance. Taking those findings into account already in the design process will be necessary to align the future of the maritime transport with the IMO sustainability goals. However, this sprawl of new technologies and fuels cannot be captured by the traditional rule-based standards and will potentially require a rethinking of the current safety assessment process.

Therefore, this paper analyses the assessment of safety for the design process when integrating alternative fuels, with a focus on hydrogen carriers. Two aspects will be discussed in detail: designing for safety with an alternative fuel and safety from the point of view of the necessary control system.

2.2. Generally used methods to assess safety

Standards and codes, such as those set up by the IMO, aim to ensure safety already in the vessel design stage. The goal is to safeguard the safety of ships, seafarers and the environment. Several techniques are currently in use to ensure this safety. The methods, also known as safety tools, discussed in the following are generally used to assess the safety of various processes and designs [13, 14, 15]. The first is fault tree analysis (FTA), with the objective to assess component failures and human errors leading to the occurrence of undesired events in the operation. Similarly, event tree analysis (ETA) can be used to quantify the possibility of consequences. With hazard and operability studies (HAZOP) the human and management factors, as well as programmable electric systems are analysed to draw conclusions for system improvements. Another safety tool, known as failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA), defines, identifies and eliminates known and potential failures, problems and errors in a system. One of the most encompassing, full-scale methods to assess risks is the quantitative risk assessment (QRA). The QRA is so well-known and widely used that the Dutch government published a book full of guidelines on how to do a QRA, the so-called purple book [16]. These types of risk assessments are also part of the Formal Safety Assessment (FSA) of the IMO, usually undertaken at step 2 of the FSA [17]. The formal safety assessment is a tool for policymakers to assess the rule making process of the IMO. Additionally, the QRA can be used to underpin compliance with the goal-based standards. Thus, a QRA often forms the basis of a large amount of safety management in general.

While there are many more [15], this selection is very commonly used in assessing safety for fuel-based transportation system or the fuels itself [18]. The aim of these tools is to detect disturbances in the process so that these can be analysed [13]. Applying those assessment methods should ultimately lead to enhanced safety and an improvement in operability. Each of these methodologies and techniques has its limitations and advantages. An overview of the main methods used to assess safety in previous literature [18], as well as a short description of these methods and their major limitations [15] can be found in table 1. From this overview, some general shortcomings that are relevant to all methods can be derived.

2.3. Shortcomings of general methods when integrating alternative fuels

Most of the issues with the previous methods are technical issues, while others are more philosophical or ethical. First of all, the engineering approach of putting numbers on assessments and then comparing them, runs into (ethical) problems quickly. What is safe? How many people are allowed to die? Is the death of a sailor worse than the death of a bystander? How many injured people are worse than a dead person? How does damage to the environment relate to all these questions? This results in many ethical questions that need to be raised, and these ethical questions are very likely to be answered differently for each of the involved stakeholders.

Table 1 Overview of methods used to assess safety of alternative fuels in literature and their major disadvantages [15, 18]

Method	Short description	Limitations
FTA (Failure Tree Analysis)	Determine component failures and human errors, which can result in the occurrence of an undesired event	State-based Diverse or multiple top events are limited No reliable results in complex relationship systems Failure probabilities as crisp numbers
HAZOP (Hazard and Operability Studies)	Focuses on analysis of human factors, management factors and programmable electric systems to improve the system	Lack of experience in HAZOP Failure to communicate changes Shortage of technical information Complex relations difficult (focus on stand-alone events) Focus on guide words only
FMEA (Failure Modes and Effects Analysis)	Define, identify, eliminate known and potential failures, problems and errors RPN (Risk Priority Number) = O (Occurrence) \times S (Severity) \times D (Not Detecting)	No relative significance of O , S or D No scientific basis No inter-dependencies or indirect relations Impact of single failure on the system
ETA (Event Tree Analysis)	Quantifies the possibility of consequences	Expert's (limited) knowledge Incomplete information Poor data quality Interpretation of failure mechanism Assumption that likelihood of events is accurate
QRA (Quantitative Risk Assessment)	Full-scale methodology which is used as a tool for comprehensive risk assessment in chemical process industry	Data quality Focuses on failure of components Does not cover all phases of plant cycle

Related to this is the desire to capture risk in a single number. The Dutch Health Council already warned in the 1990s that risk cannot be captured by a single number [13]. Quantifying risks in one number may result in disagreements between the calculated risks and those perceived by non-experts or citizens, which in turn may result in distrust of experts. Focusing too much on quantitative, number-based methods of assessing risk and, to an extent, safety should thus be avoided.

Next to these ethical questions, there are also more practical questions when trying to capture risk in numbers. Besides risk, often defined as probability times consequences [19], there are other parts that are often categorised as risk, but can also be considered as different principles [19, 20]. Other forms which are relevant for this research: scenario uncertainty, ignorance, indeterminacy and normative uncertainties [20]. Scenario uncertainty is defined as not knowing all failure mechanisms, which is required for all methods mentioned in table 1. The entire system has to be known in detail, and exact knowledge of what is happening (e.g. chemical processes) and where this is happening has to be available. All of these techniques are based on finding out where there may be failure mechanisms and what their result can be. However, when designing a future ship, much is unknown in the early design phase, whilst a sufficient amount of details is required to estimate the different failure modes.

In addition to scenario uncertainty, ignorance is also an issue. With ignorance, neither all failure mechanisms nor all undesirable consequences are known. This can also be seen from table 1, as practical data on failure is required to quantify risks. This data is often lacking, which results in an uncertainty margin on the desired numerical outcome. This margin is usually at least one order of magnitude, but can be up to five orders of magnitude [13, 14]. This issue has been known since 1982. Indeterminacy can also be seen as the human factor: the user operating the system in a way that was not foreseen [20]. This happens often, also in the maritime domain [21]. Automating processes may make it easier to quantify things (as quantifying human behaviour is extremely difficult [13]). However, this removes the main advantage of a human: the ability to think and improvise quickly. Humans have shown to be able to accomplish great things this way, as is shown by United Airlines Flight 232 [22]. After all hydraulics failed, the crew was still able to fly the plane by operating only its engines [22]. Even though such exceptional cases have not happened in the shipping industry, quick thinking did save the passengers of the MV Viking Sky, which ran into trouble after a loss of oil pressure in a rough sea [23]. Blindly removing the human factor, to automate and be able to quantify more easily, may thus not be the best course of action. As removing the human can lead to unforeseen issues, caution should be exercised when considering this.

The final category is normative uncertainties. Normative uncertainty is uncertainty about how to act in

Figure 1 Hydrogen carrier process diagram, including indication which technologies are mature and less-mature

certain situations [20]. Because of the relative novelty of all alternative fuels, normative uncertainties are very likely to occur, as not all scenarios can be envisioned and trained for. These uncertainties cannot easily be anticipated, although it is of extreme importance to not only train the easy scenarios [24]. Even though this may sound obvious, training of only simplified scenarios is likely to have contributed to the sinking of the Ocean Ranger [24]. Summarised, all these techniques have shortcomings. This is captured very well by other authors such as Basheer et al.: "it is not possible to analyse all the aspects of a system using any single technique" [15]. Similarly, Taebi et al. mentioned that preventable accidents, such as the Fukushima Daichii incident, are a sobering warning against overconfidence in hazard prediction [20]. This is especially critical, as several methods assume perfect human performance, which is not realistic on ships [20, 21]. Most of these methods have the possibility of taking the human factor in account, even though in reality this is often omitted. For example, Skogdalen et al. [25] researched whether QRAs, in the oil and gas industry, took into account human and organizational factors, as most accidents have a social, administrative or managerial origin [13]. They found that none of the QRAs reached the level at which human and organizational factors are taken into account best. Most did not take the human and organisational factors into account (5 out of 15), or only explained it to a limited extent (8 out of 15) [25]. It is challenging to systematically include quantitative estimates on the impact of human factors and organisational impacts on failure in a QRA [25].

3. Designing for Safety when using Alternative fuels

Mentioning what is wrong with previous methods is not difficult, nor is it innovative or particularly useful. Moving forward, towards how safety can be incorporated in the design phase of a ship fueled by an alternative fuel is much more relevant. We can learn from other sectors, such as aviation and chemical industry and how they have incorporated safety in their respective designs. Yet, more importantly, we can look at the field of safety science, and learn lessons from many places on how designs affect safety.

The use of hydrogen carriers inevitably complicates the design. Figure 1 gives an overview of the alternative process, which now incorporates specialised fuel preparations and additional tanks to store the spent fuel, next to the energy converter (e.g. an internal combustion engine or fuel cell) to deliver the required power to the ship. Especially the tanks and the fuel preparation unit come with many unknowns, as these are likely new technology on this scale and in this environment.

This section will move from the shortcomings of the previously mentioned methods of assessing safety and risk, towards potential ways of incorporating safety science to deal with safety in a different way, with a focus on hydrogen carriers as alternative fuels onboard ships.

3.1. From quantifying risks to an integral approach

Currently, the results of a QRA or similar safety tool often form the basis of risk management [25]. A QRA should also be used to reveal the status of the so-called safety barriers: means that prevent, control or mitigate undesired events or accidents [25, 13]. These barriers can be physical, such as cofferdams, but this is not necessary. However, quantification methods, such as QRAs, face comparable challenges when applied during the design phase, especially when alternative fuels are incorporated. First of all, as mentioned previously, they depend on data from previous accidents, which is unlikely to be available for new technology like hydrogen carriers. This can result in large uncertainties in a QRA. Secondly, QRAs also suffer from underreporting of non-lethal accidents. Accidents that are only minor, are often not reported as it is not deemed significant [13]. Another issue with the QRA is the illusion of equal comparison: when everything is expressed as numbers, it appears as though these can be compared. However, this often leads to confusion among non-experts and difficult ethical decisions. This becomes more apparent with fuels that already have a certain reputation with the public, such as ammonia. Even though orders for ships that can be powered by ammonia are plenty [26, 27], public opinion is very much against it [28]. At least the UK public prefers virtually any other fuel, including nuclear and heavy fuel oil, over the usage of ammonia [28].

Finally, the most important issue with the QRA for alternative fuels is the inclusion of human factors, which is not adequately considered. However, human performance and behaviour gain increased importance when handling new and potentially hazardous fuels. Another issue arises with a common solution for the problem of the human factor: automation. Often, engineers see automation as enhancing the safety of a process, as using automation is thought to lead to cause-and-effect relationships, which in turn can be quantified [13]. However, automation comes with multiple issues. Directly related to the QRA is the following: when significantly changing a process, which can occur when using e.g. robots, it does not necessarily result in less incidents, it might even result in a less well-founded QRA as the dominant accident scenarios might change [13]. As using alternative fuels already significantly alters the system, with many lesser-known process steps (as visible in figure 1), the dominant accident scenarios will likely already change compared to the conventional process. This will also increase the chance of completely overlooking accident scenarios, which is not unheard of [20]. Adding automation to this, changing it even further, will likely result in different dominant accident scenarios. Additionally, people learn by trial and error, by making mistakes and taking risks. These learnings are needed to understand the entire process and adequately respond to accidents [13].

Consequently, it is not possible to assess the safety of a hydrogen carrier system to the highest detail in the design stage momentarily using the current methods, as several problems arise due to the uncertainties inherent to the process. Combined, this shows that estimating all risks in advance in detail may not be possible when using alternative fuels such as hydrogen carriers on ships, due to the many complications and unknowns they bring. The Collingridge dilemma is relevant here: the more we know, so the further we are in the design phase, the more we will know of the related risks, but our control over it all grows less [20]. Thus, we have to move on from this rational image of trying to find an integral approach towards a more contextual picture.

3.2. From a rational image to a contextual picture: Incorporating the Human Factor

Even though the engineering approach is to reduce the human influence and presence as much as possible, especially when using "dangerous" alternative fuels, such as ammonia, this may not directly be the perfect course [13]. The most important reasoning for this is that humans are good at quick problem-solving, not repetitive tasks. Additionally, as mentioned previously, humans learn by trial and error, and have several ways to learn. For example, humans should not learn from books how to react in emergency situations, but from experience and thus, practising these kind of situations [21]. If the human factor is completely removed from the system, the human's understanding of the system will be reduced. This is highly problematic in case humans are expected to solve the problem [21]. Yet, it is true that humans, or better worded the human and operational factor, is the cause of many accidents. However, this does not necessarily mean that a process with many possibly dangerous factors is directly correlating to many accidents. An example as mentioned by [13] tells of an industrial location, where everything could hurt people,

Figure 2 How to design with keeping humans in mind

yet with an exceptionally high amount of days without accidents. So, it is possible for humans to operate in dangerous conditions without failure. Incorporating the human factor in the design of a ship, especially a ship with such complex and possibly dangerous additions as when using hydrogen carriers as alternative fuels, is thus of utmost importance.

When entering the human in design, it is important to take into account the human's good and bad qualities. Humans have physical and mental limitations. Physical limitations should be incorporated at all times, and are, for example, health hazards or (very) heavy lifting. Time-critical operations are better avoided as well. Human operation in rooms with high temperatures, high noise levels or strong vibrations, such as in an engine room, is also detrimental to human functioning. Other human limitations are mental. Humans do not do well with repetition, so that should be avoided. Besides, over- and understimulation of human senses should be prevented. Additionally, in the maritime domain, 71% of the errors involving humans are caused by a lack of situational awareness [21]. Situational awareness has gained a lot of attention in the aviation sector, from which the maritime industry could benefit [21]. Situational awareness should not be confused with the awareness of danger: even people with high motivation and the highest degree of safety awareness will have accidents [29]. Improving motivation and awareness is also a dead-end: much has been done on that level, and it is assumed not much more is possible [29]. The most effective way to improve safety is by changing the environment [29]. The focus should be on ensuring that all technology is designed from a human-centred perspective and aligned with maritime needs [21]. For example, when alarms are used, it should be instantly clear which alarm is going off, which is not always the case [21]. A proper work environment has to be created [29]. Other factors are more operational, such as avoiding victim blaming and catering the training and inspection to the specific ship, instead of having general employee training [13]. Figure 2 gives an overview of both the design and operational aspects of incorporating the human factor to enhance the safety of ships.

3.3. How to deal with Uncertainties

Finally, uncertainty will still exist even when incorporating the human factor during the design and operation. Hindsight cannot save us [24], we have to look ahead into the unknown. Engineers often try to make the system foolproof and in shipping especially changing the hardware is a traditional approach to solving a problem, even if that problem was the result of human error [29]. However, there are several issues with this approach. First of all, behaviour of humans can be unexpected. Secondly, people will try to look for loopholes to make their life easier, yet undermining the foolproofness of the system [29]. Trying to make a system foolproof is thus expensive, but with low effect. Additionally, when adding complexity, foolproofing is even more difficult. It is clear that complex interactive processes and tight coupling of steps

Figure 3 System complexity increase by change of conventional energy system design towards interconnected systems.

make accidents inevitable and, worse, unforeseen by designers nor understood by operators [13]. Most of the principles to operating high-reliability organisations lie on operational level. Examples are the detection of small failures anywhere or the differentiation of categories [22]. Basically all accidents have had some form of precursor incidents happening before the actual accident [24]. However, one of the principles is related to the design of the process, the principle of sensitivity to operations [22]. The aim of this principle is to set apart the work itself, seeing what we are doing instead of focussing on intentions or designs [22]. This can be attributed to the resilience of the system: a system that can continue to function as required, even after a serious incident has occurred [22]. The function as required does not mean the system is completely intact; the system just has to be able to continue the required operations, albeit in a degraded form [22]. In practical terms, in the design we should stimulate a system with graceful degradation and avoid a system performance with a single point of failure. Interestingly, the alternative fuel system configurations give these opportunities: high numbers of cells in batteries and stacks in fuel cells give graceful degradation options, where traditional internal combustion engines might fail with one driving gear failure. In real life, with all its uncertainties and unexpected events, coping with the unexpected and having an anticipatory mind-set is more important than anticipating occurrences [22]. Precise identification of issues is not always possible in an emergency situation, so a combination of keeping errors checked, improvising such that the system keeps functioning (even if only minimally) and absorbing change while persisting is required [22].

4. Designing for safe and more complex control systems

The second part of this study focuses on the role of control systems and their role for safety onboard vessels, particularly their ability to manage dynamic and unpredictable scenarios. The increasing electrification of vessel design in the recent years [9] allows for the integration of modern technologies into the energy system. This includes energy storage technologies to enhance the efficiency of energy usage onboard, as well as the use of alternative fuels for energy generation itself [30, 31, 32, 33], which are often accompanied by additional components for fuel preparation or dispensation of spent-fuel. However, with the increasing interconnectivity of those novel power train configurations, the complexity of the energy system onboard and its operation rises [10]. This is illustrated in figure 3, where the new interconnection of the system components offers greater flexibility of operation, but also increases the control options. This complexity increase presents an increasing challenge for the commonly used rule-based control, which are the state of the art in the operation of vessel energy systems [34]. As a consequence, the design of a vessel using alternative fuels is not only a safety consideration from the fuel aspect, but also influences the safety of the control system due to the increased complexity of the operation.

A common reaction in the scientific research community to address this increased complexity and to

Figure 4 Aspects of safety for control systems onboard vessels.

ensure the optimality of the vessel energy system operation are advanced control methods [8]. Those approaches vary from optimization-based to predictive or even data-driven methods and can range in scope from operation of energy system parts or components up to complete energy system control or even autonomous vessels [35]. This makes a generic comparison harder as the approaches to ensure the operation of the system vary greatly. Therefore, the influence of control systems onto the safety assessment onboard of a vessel can be split up into different aspects.

4.1. How safety relates to the control system of a vessel

The term of safety for vessel control can be discussed in several aspects focusing on different areas of operation, which is illustrated in figure 4. The safety of the operator focuses on the human factor, mainly keeping the crew and passengers onboard as safe as possible. Further, the operational safety needs to be ensured, meaning to sustain the ability of the vessel to perform its intended task. Breaking this down from the vessel task to the system itself, the last aspect is the upkeep of the internal system. This means protecting the components of the system from failure and harmful influences from the side of the control. In the following, all aspects are further discussed in detail.

Control systems for operator safety The first safety aspect onboard, which can be influenced by the control system design is the safety of the operator. This refers to safeguarding the operator by employing control mechanisms that reduce the potential for harm towards humans. This starts with using automated component control to remove the task of operating the components by hand and extends to the possibility to fully automate complete chains of processes. Automated processes such as for example a combined fuel preparation, energy conversion and left-over storage chain allow to restrict the access of humans to areas of the energy system. This allows the human to operate the machinery from the safety of a central control room [36]. This idea is also represented in the complete automation of vessels, which is a concept discussed for the introduction of potentially hazardous fuels, such as ammonia. While this idea drastically increases the safety of humans onboard by removing them from the vessel, it also opens up various other safety concerns such as crisis management, leakage prevention and the ability to deal with a potential system failure as control systems are also not completely fault-proof [37].

Control systems for operational safety The second safety aspect onboard in regards to the control system is the safety of the operation. In this, the control system is used to ensure the continuous and undisturbed upkeep of the vessels intended function. This includes operational tasks such as travel, transport or other works, as well as auxiliary tasks such as heating or electricity supply. All those tasks require energy generated from the energy system. This requires the system control to fulfil all needs of requested energy in the time of their occurrence and to manage the energy system accordingly. This includes the generation of mechanical energy, as well as satisfying the thermal and electrical energy demands. Therefore, the system control is subdivided into the control of the energy system and other potential control tasks, such as navigation or other ship functions. Commonly, ensuring the safe upkeep of their respective operation is the

primary task of every control system in itself. When designed correctly and operating as intended, control systems allow for a more precise operation than humans could manage [36].

Control systems for systemic safety The third aspect to discuss regarding safety onboard influenced by the control system is the safety of the system in itself. This is an important aspect, as it is the fundament to ensure the safety of the discussed above aspects. It includes the energy system, but also all other onboard systems influenced by a control system. Conceptually this aspect relates to ensuring the operation of all components inside their allowed ranges for operation or by limiting the use of harmful states for a component to a minimum. While this is critical to keep up the operational safety, the internal safety of the system also contributes to the operator safety as it reduces the manual maintenance necessary. This is often done by constraints of the controller.

4.2. Assessing the actual safety of control systems

Even after defining the different aspects of how the control system of the vessel can influence safety, one question needs to be raised: How can this safety be assessed and ensured? This is especially important as vessels can face dynamic and unpredictable scenarios in their daily operation. A vessel control system is required to be functioning in every scenario, as it directly relates to the safety of humans onboard, the operation and the system itself, as discussed previously. Proving this presents a challenge, especially for advanced control methods, which are far more complex than the commonly used rule-based control strategies. Using advanced control, we still need to ensure that the expected outcome of the control is situated inside a pre-defined solution space and therefore limit the influence from uncertainties [38]. To prove this, the field introduced the term robustness to describe this inherent quality and its highly theoretical background [39]. Robustness describes the input-output space for which the control can be expected to always end up in this pre-approved solution space. In less technical terms, this means a mathematical proof of safety against failure to find an adequate control solution. However, getting this proof is not always easy, as it is inherently connected to the mathematical properties of the problem. While it is relatively easy to show robustness of linear problems, which the world hardly ever is, showing robustness of non-linear or non-convex problems is a challenge. Still, trying to show the robustness and therefore provide an estimation of the safety of the system itself is a required step for the integration of advanced control strategies into the design of future vessels.

5. Insights for safe vessel design

Many steps can be taken to improve the safety of a vessel starting in the design process. This section outlines several methods for enhancing safety, as summarised in figure 5. On the left side of the figure are the measures that should always be taken. These standard measures are very relevant, and are the first steps to control safety during design [21]. The first step is the removal of the problem. If an alternative fuel is such an extent unsafe in a certain context, it should not be used at all. Secondly, if a certain fuel is absolutely necessary, yet not entirely safe, a barrier should be put around it to avoid incidents outside its area of operation. These two steps have to be taken during the earlier design process, while the third step, implementation of warnings, can be taken later on.

However, only taking these steps is not sufficient. Robust design of components and all included control systems is required as well. Especially, the disturbance-free operation of critical infrastructure needs to be ensured and designed appropriately. While this is easier to ensure for simple component controls, it presents a challenge when moving towards autonomous or advanced control approaches. When implementing the latter, proving their robustness under operation gets more difficult. For optimization-based control approaches the difficulty lies in the mathematical complexity of the system. Therefore, directly proving that an advanced control of an operation is safe in the design process might not be possible, as is visible in figure 5: a clear distinction between linear systems and complex, non-linear and non-convex systems is made.

Another option to prove the fail-safety of advanced control of the vessel operation is the more time-consuming trial-and-error for the algorithm. This way, a statistical approach could be used to identify the

Figure 5 Insights in how to design a safe, alternative-fuelled vessel using a multifaceted approach

spread of expected outputs for a set of inputs. However, using this approach allows for an understanding of the algorithms accuracy, but cannot completely neglect the possibility of the algorithm ending up in a not-desired solution. Still, it can be considered a first step towards the application of advanced control algorithms that can improve the safety of the human and operation. To enhance safety, the focus should lie on minimizing the necessary complexity of the system during the design process. Even though this might lead into a higher fuel usage, it helps create more reliable and failproof control systems. This all contributes to a vessel that is designed as safe as possible; however all these procedures will not result in a foolproof, 100% safe ship. In addition, besides the three main steps, the overall technical process should still be evaluated using current methods as mentioned in table 1. However, the precaution should exist that these are limited and additional investigation is required. Additionally, the human factor should be taken into account within these risk assessments.

Moreover, the procedures focus mainly on the safety of the ship, yet the human factor is extremely important, too. To make the ship more safe while incorporating humans, the human operator should be taken into account directly during the design phase. Processes should be designed such that humans do what they are good at: varied tasks, that are within the scope of the human capability, without crossing physical or mental limits of humans. Linear systems are often easier to automate than complex systems. Automating everything is not the solution, but automating certain tasks is part of the solution. Tasks that should be automated are for example tasks that are not compatible with the human physics, such as tasks that threaten human health, or human lives, tasks that exceed the physical limits (which may be legally limited) of humans, and tasks for which humans are too slow. Other tasks to automate are those that do not comply with the human mind. Examples are monotone or predictable work, as well as overstimulation of the human mind by data flooding. Finally, for some tasks the human perception is insufficient. A major sidenote to this, is that tasks or processes that are highly influential for the safety on board, should not be automated completely: humans are much better at responding and (creatively) fixing problems of processes that they know much about, than if they have to deal with less-familiar processes.

Besides, during design phase, human and operational factors should be considered. Indeterminacy (humans not using systems as envisioned) should be taken into account, for example by multiple simulations with the process and humans, especially in less-than-ideal situations, but also in common situations. Additionally, products should be designed user-friendly, something that was often not the case in the maritime industry [21]. Finally, the situational awareness of humans has to be taken into account within design.

During the design phase, the two most important things to acknowledge are the following. First of all, no design is inherently safe and the uncertain will always happen. Secondly, design is only part of the whole process, operation is at least equally, if not more, important for safety.

5.1. Operation

Figure 5 has an additional part, which we have not discussed until now: the operational factor. Even though the operation of the ship is not in the scope of this research, we will discuss some of the key-insights of safety science how and why extremely dangerous and complex workplaces can have very limited (to even no) accidents.

Safe operation is one of the most important ways to enhance safety [13, 40]. The operational aspects and, as a result, whether a system is error-inducing, error-neutral or error-reducing, is often considered more relevant to safety than tightly coupled or highly complex systems [40]. A good, safe operation and a safety-focussed operation will result in a safer environment, yet unfortunately safety and efficiency are often regarded as opposing forces, especially in the shipping industry [41, 40]. Cost-efficient operation is part of organisational behaviour [13]. However, safety and (cost)-efficiency are not necessarily opposites, process intensification in chemical engineering and management, for example, does not have safety as prime target, yet results in safer processes regardless [13].

A large part of safe operation is the removal of victim blaming [13], which is often prominent in error-inducing systems [40]. Companies that are likely to dismiss, punish and blame people, are less likely to learn from incidents and accidents [13]. The international safety management code (ISM)-code from the IMO supports this [21, 42]. The ISM code specifically states that good safety management is commitment from the top [42]. Additionally, the ISM code requires companies to develop safety management systems and preparations for emergencies, as well as requiring companies to report incidents and accidents [42]. However, a drawback of this code is that whilst a shipping organisation may be compliant to the ISM code, it does not mean that the system is actually effective [21]. Not only is it hard for organisations and individuals to adhere to the code, the motivation to comply to the code also varies [21].

In general, the shipping sector has for long been regarded as an error-inducing system [40]. Despite this observation being older, made in 1986, it unfortunately remains relevant today. Error-prone systems are not easily changed, despite regulations like the ISM-code [21, 40, 42]. The social organisation, economic pressure, structure of the industry, influence of insurance companies and difficulties of national and international regulations (which are often both relevant), still operate in such a way to resist solutions to reduce errors [40]. An example of how all these come together in one accident is the sinking of *El Faro* in 2015. *El Faro* disappeared with all hands as it sailed through the Caribbean in 2015 [43]. The main actions identified were the decision (by the captain) to sail in close proximity to a hurricane and not complying to the ISM code, as not all the material was in good order and no necessary shoreside support was available [43]. This only underscores the difficulty of change, as the underlying, social organisational issues have been known for many years already [40].

Often mentioned as problematic are the different cultures of the crew on board ships [13, 40, 41]. However, this appears to be a relative weak argument, as the aviation sector has similarly diverse crews, yet does not see this as a problem [41]. In the aviation sector, the protocols are of such a standard that local culture is not deemed to be relevant [41]. This is one of many operational differences between the shipping and aviation industry, where the aviation industry can be regarded as much further ahead safety-wise [41]. This also highlights the difference between error-inducing and error-reducing systems: the aviation system is an error-reducing system and thus language is less of a problem [40]. However, lessons can still be learned from the aviation system: especially the training (including human factor training), safety reports, automation, situation awareness and implementation of a just culture and a safety culture are mentioned as very promising [41]. Perrow's examination of the more distant past—spanning the late 19th to early 20th century—reveals a rather discouraging continuity, as he notes little substantive progress during that period [40]. More than three decades later, a similar assessment may still hold: operational advancements remain limited, and implementing substantial change continues to pose significant challenges.

6. Conclusion

Safety is of high importance in the maritime sector. Many methods are used to assess the safety of ships. However, current methods often overlook the human factor, which in turn is regarded as the main cause of many maritime accidents. Safety science can be used to avoid this. Safety science teaches us that human failure is often the result of design, organisational or operational problems, and not a cause on its own. Taking human failure into account is difficult, due to a lack of data, scenario uncertainty, indeterminacy and more. Due to the uncertainty characterised by future accidents and incidents, it is impossible to use a watertight approach to designing a safe vessel. Yet, good design can account for a vessel that is at least safer. When we look from a safety science perspective, we see the following. There are several standard steps, which should always be taken. These steps are: removing problems, placing barriers and implementation of warnings. Additionally, uncertainty needs to be embraced and complex interactive processes and tight coupling of steps should be avoided or simplified. The system's sensitivity to incidents should be reduced, part of which can be assessed by checking the robustness of the system. However, all this only covers part of enhancing the safety. To optimally design a safe vessel, all systems, processes and technology have to be designed with the human in mind. Despite all these measures, design is only one part; the operation of the vessel is equally important in enhancing its safety. A safe working culture with a focus on safety and less on efficiency is required for safer ships. The shipping industry has much to learn here, particularly from the field of safety science, which emphasizes systemic thinking, resilience, and learning from near-misses as well as failures. Finally, the notion that nothing can be inherently safe and that accidents can always happen is something that should always be in the back of everybody's mind: expect the unexpected. That, combined with optimal human and machine collaboration will result in safer vessels and thus, a safer shipping sector.

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